

**IMPORTANT PRINCIPLES OF TEACHING ENGLISH AND
IMPLEMENTING THEM IN FLUENT AND CONSISTENT SPEECH**

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Abstract: This conceptual paper presents diverse approaches and strategies for preparing competent teachers who work with either English Language Learners (ELLs) or students who speak English as a Second Language (ESL). The pedagogical approaches discussed herein include practical and hands-on activities for teachers at any level. Bilingual learning improves ELL's cognitive development as well as their self-esteem. The paper outlines underlying principles for the best practices with an emphasis on ESL students and also to other learning situations and students. Teachers can modify their instructional methods to adjust ELL's learning needs. Specifically, even though the discussion is framed in the context of ESL students in U.S. classrooms, it is applicable to TEFL (Teaching English as a Foreign Language) environments in schools and other centers of learning.

Keywords: English as Second Language (ESL), English Language Learner (ELL), Teaching English to Speakers of Other Languages (TESOL), bilingual learners, teaching strategies

Nowadays, the problem of developing creative abilities in adolescents is especially relevant in the process of teaching English. In the modern context of the pedagogical process of secondary schools, this is an important scientific problem of historical, ethnic, cultural and socio-pedagogical significance. The development of creative abilities of school students is not possible without generalizing the experience of using English lessons in the system of education and upbringing. The study of English, its history of development, folk culture and daily life is one of the conditions not only for students to learn English, but also for teaching a foreign

language and developing the creative abilities of schoolchildren on specific life material should be considered as. The formation of creative abilities in adolescents is based on the development of creative thinking and, in particular, components such as:

- Analytical components – accordingly, conceptual and logical thinking – consistency, mobility, selectivity, associativity, intelligence, ability to differentiate, etc .;
- Emotional components (emotional-figurative thinking): the brightness of images, emotional evaluation of events, facts, events, etc.
- Creative components (visual-effective thinking): the search for rational solutions, non-standard (individuality, originality, freedom from stereotypes), the ability to predict the outcome, the desire to synthesize the best knowledge and skills in the activity , the ability to choose the most optimal solution from the available options and justify the right choice.

The teacher should guide the students, contributing to the development of their creative abilities in each lesson. Only in the process of purposeful diligence it is possible to form certain qualities and achieve interest in the lesson. The diversity of didactic work creates different purposeful relationships in students, the time spent on independent work increases. Acquiring knowledge, skills and abilities to work independently teaches students to work creatively, develops creative thinking, creates the preconditions for their application in the system of professional activity, improves oral and written communication skills, thinking, feeling -prefers to express feelings and emotions, as well as the ability to think. The more different tasks are used, the more effective the results will be.

Most clearly, students 'areas of creative activity are reflected in their hobbies. They make something out of natural and other metals, they love literature, they keep diaries, they take photos, they collect collections, they communicate with nature, they correspond with foreign friends, they do things out of the ordinary and out of the ordinary. Looking for things and so on. Such hobbies can be used to increase cognitive activity. Student activity in foreign language classes. At the request of

the teacher, the children bring to the lessons from their collections photos, postcards, letters, objects that enliven the communication in a foreign language, which will be more meaningful, close and interesting for its participants. The task of the teacher is to study and know in depth the hobbies of the school students, to use them for the creative expression of the students in the classroom.

In the general methodology of teaching foreign languages, the method is considered as a method of orderly interaction of teacher and students (within the system). In this sense, the method is carried out by technical means, the choice of which is determined by the basics of the education system. The content of foreign language teaching cannot be determined without reference to linguistics, which studies languages as specific code systems. People use language (code system) to communicate; communicate through them. The methodology explores the problems associated with foreign language teaching – a code that is comprehensively studied in linguistics.

Thus, linguistics describes the norm of language, that is, the set of rules (rules) governing the accepted speech use of language tools, the use of language tools in a person's speech. It is important to differentiate science, language, and speech for foreign language teaching methods. Modern linguistics understands language as a code of social significance and its rules of operation, which is entrenched in the minds of a group of people. In other words, language is a system of language tools and rules of use required for communication. Speech is understood as the implementation of a language system in certain acts of communication. The concept of "speech" includes both the process itself and the products of this process – speech works. Although language and speech form two sides of a phenomenon, a whole, they act with units specific to each side.

Speaking – an effective visual speech activity, through which (along with listening) verbal communication is carried out. The content of speech is the verbal expression of thought. Speech is based on pronunciation, lexical, grammatical skills. In many teaching methods, speech is one of the most important areas of teaching. Depending on the major or minor role of programming, statements distinguish between

initiative (active) speech, reactive (response) speech, and reproductive (stochastic) speech. The psychological structure of speech movement involves four stages:

- 1) motivational-motivational, in which the person's need for communication is reflected in the influence of a particular motive and the presence of a specific purpose of the statement;
- 2) analytical-synthetic, presented in the form of folded mental actions for programming and forming ideas (there is a mechanism of internal formation of the statement, which provides word selection and grammatical prediction);
- 3) The executive sound and intonation design of the thought (at the initial stage of learning, the transition of the speech program to its execution takes place through the native language;
- 4) control, its function is to signal possible errors and contribute to their correction; control implies that the speaker has a norm that is formed as a result of language practice and comparison of his speech with the norm.

Speech training has been developed in preparation and special exercises divided into speech. In communication, the skills and abilities of unprepared speech, its reactivity, spontaneity, topic are developed; skills and abilities with the initiative, logic, consistency of the prepared speech – in a monologue. Dialogic speech is a form of speech in which there is a direct exchange of statements between two or more persons. The conditions for the continuation of dialogic speech determine a number of its features, including: brevity of speech, widespread use of non-verbal communication (facial expressions, gestures), the large role of intonation, the diversity of special sentences. Incomplete composition, the syntactic design of a sentence free from the strict norms of book speech, the predominance of simple sentences. Dialogic speech teaching unit Dialogic unit (microdialog) – several copies related to the content and form.

When teaching dialogic speech, it is recommended to use different types of dialogues and different forms of working with them: dialogue-dialogue, dialogue-staging, student interaction and teacher, pair and group conversation. The main means of teaching dialogic speech are exercises. In the process of implementing

them, skills are formed: asking for information, responding adequately to the words of the interlocutor, using the clichés of dialogic speech, combining feedback in building a dialogue, and so on.

A teacher who can “purposefully exhibit a wide range of teaching styles is potentially able to accomplish more than a teacher whose repertoire is relatively limited” (Smith & Renzulli, 1984, p. 49). Due to the availability of multiple platforms of communication and learning, innovative ways to deliver instruction are evolving. Dunn and Dunn (1979) found that only 20-30% of school-age children appear to be auditory learners, that 40% are visual, and that the remaining 30-40% are tactile/kinesthetic, visual/tactile, or some other combination. Researchers have found that early on children tend to be mostly tactile/kinesthetic and gradually they develop other strengths such as visual and auditory (Price, Dunn, and Sanders (1980). Multiple learning modalities (such as read it, write, do it, and talk it, see it, hear it, interact with it) are used in the integrated approach. Teachers can use multimedia and other technologies in lessons incorporating websites to enrich visual support for the learners. Teachers use interactive teaching style and various learning modalities to meet the needs of their ESL students. New modalities have changed multimodal digital platforms that present educators with the possibility of providing meaningful opportunities for engagement and creativity employing different cognitive, audio-visual senses and ability to interact.

Teachers can now provide audio feedback to students which is shown to provide more elaborate detailed responses where teachers provide not only more information but the richer language and greater elaboration of concepts (Swan-Dagen, et al., 2008). Technologies like ClassDojo have the ability to translate material for teachers, and teachers can print, email, or text the information they need to send to students’ parents as necessary. Rewordify.com is free and child safe online software that improves reading and learning. One can enter difficult or complex sentences or text passages in the highlighted box, and the program rewords the text into simpler text and voila! One can even click on a phrase or a difficult word to hear it, thus addressing the pronunciation aspect as well.

Students can create scripts and manage illustrations to go with the scripts. Engagement level in the students goes up as they work on media projects. Students can use Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, YouTube, blog posts as social media to share thoughts and ideas or create digital stories. Online forums for discussion provide an opportunity for a wider range of responses than a traditional discussion where the first respondents set the tone for an entire group. ESL students may feel more comfortable as they post their views in online forums. It provides space for the development of unique learner's voices, ideas, thoughts, and opinions.

Speech is the expression of one's thoughts to solve communication problems. It is a person's activity, even if he is involved in communication and is unimaginable outside of it, because communication is always a interaction with other people. The product of communication is the interpretation of information. There are three modes of communication: cognitive, interactive, and informative, as well as two types of communication: role-playing and personal. These are the main features of communication. The principle of speech orientation also involves the use of communicatively valuable speech material. The use of each phrase should be based on the intended communication area (situation) and the communicative value for that category of students. The verbal nature of the lesson also plays an important role here. Functionality primarily determines the selection and organization of material that is appropriate to the communication process.

An approach to communication needs is only possible if the means of speech are taken into account and the material is organized around situations and speech tasks rather than around conversation topics and grammatical events. The unity of lexical, grammatical and phonetic aspects of speech is also necessary. Speech activity is based on the transfer of skills, as the infinitely changing conditions of communication place new tasks on the speaker each time. If the speech skills that are the basis of the skill are potentially permeable and therefore the speech skills are dynamic enough, they can be tackled. Conditional speech situations are a condition for the formation of situational flexibility of speech skills. They create all the conditions for some kind of speech unit, under special conditions (regularity of use,

pattern) suitable for automating the speech pattern, without losing the situation (usually typical of training exercises).

A very good context for the activity can be provided by special films. These event films should have a communicative (taking into account the field of communication), methodological character in terms of content (problem), direction. Such a film is shown before each lesson cycle and introduces students to the environment of subsequent events, based on which the teacher creates situations in the classroom. Not all learning material relies on film events, but expands and develops them as a means of teaching speech (texts used to develop speech, microtexts for mastering words and speech patterns). With the exception of exercises in the development of speech skills, the content of many training exercises could be determined by the situation. The introduction of the context of the activity is a prerequisite for the individualization of situations.

The speech statement in the methodology of teaching a foreign language takes the form of a unit of study. This can be an example of a word, phrase, speech sample, or a typical sentence, sample dialogue, or a monologue statement that is longer than a sentence on a topic or topic. A structural group that combines statements of a different nature (affirmation, denial, exhortation, interrogation) can act as a learning unit. Working with such speech units helps to shape the language system. The training units themselves are real suggestions related to specific situations. They are pronounced with a certain intonation, depending on the communicative intention, in terms of language norms, grammatical and lexical design. The content of foreign language teaching is influenced by a field of linguistics, such as sociolinguistics, which studies the relationship between language and culture, language and society. As mentioned above, language is one of the main characteristics of a nation, in which it represents the national culture of the speaking people. Therefore, it is necessary to teach a foreign language not only as a new code (method of expression), but also as a source of information about the national culture of the people. Language performs two main functions: communicative and cumulative. Understanding the importance of teaching a foreign language in close connection with national culture

is important in strengthening international cooperation. The modern methodology of teaching a foreign language is characterized by a desire to incorporate information about geography, history, social life into the content of teaching – speech material and, in particular, texts for listening and reading. This methodological position has been defined by the term *linguo-cultural*. Linguistic and cultural teaching helps students to master natural, historical realities, spiritual values, and thus helps to achieve the goal of education – the events, facts that students learn in the language they are learning. Interpreting settings. It also helps to shape linguistic consciousness.

Functional linguistics, which studies the function of language as a means of communication, a means of social interaction, describing the semantic and communicative aspects of language, has had a great influence on the methodology of teaching foreign languages. Representatives of the Council of Europe – Van Ek, J. Trim and others – have made a significant contribution to the development of a communicative approach to foreign language teaching in general, and in particular to the understanding of the theory of communicative competence. Learning tools are called material objects that can replace the teacher in their functions or help him to perform these functions. They are:

Basic

Auxiliary

For the teacher

For students

Hearing (sound recording)

Visual (pictures, tables)

Visual hearing (film, video)

Technician

Not technical

An important step in helping ESL students succeed is building their confidence and comfort level by making them feel welcome in the classroom. This pays great dividends in terms of academic success as they build positive relationships with their

academic community, teacher, peer, paraprofessionals, resource teacher, and other classroom volunteers.

Making the instructional classroom environment, welcoming and comfortable to students is critical in learning as it helps to build a relationship with ESL students.

Let there be a sense of

Openness, students should perceive the teacher as caring and thoughtful that you care about them and want to be there for them. Some ways are to bring a students' culture into the classroom by using visuals and pictures of student's cultural tradition or festivals or foods with labels in both languages is a good start. Labeling items in the classroom in two or three languages benefits them visually. They come to see that their language, heritage, and culture is valued. It also allows for opportunities for them to share about their culture. Always be consistent and fair with all students. Grouping students with a respectable and trustworthy partner can help guide when the teacher is not available. This is beneficial not only for ESL student but also for the partner, as both are learning about each other's culture and vocabulary, or when feasible, inviting a staff member from the school who speaks the student's language to work with the student. Grouping or pairing students with friends that speak the same language greatly helps the ESL student in case they are not getting what the teacher says. Other students chime in to translate the assignment in the native language to assist them with directions. Technologies like Remind and ClassDojo all have the ability to translate material for teachers, and teachers can print, email, or text the information they need to send to their parents as necessary.

Keeping instructions simple and clear is helpful. Posting the visual colorful class schedule in a prominent place in the room is helpful. Also, reviewing it daily as a set routine will reinforce it. Learn to say their name correctly. It makes a monumental difference. Students see that you not only respect their ideas, thoughts and knowledge but most of all their identity, who they are, represented by their name. Teachers can relate to their students by playing the music from the student's culture during center time or transitional times or by displaying books from the country/culture of students in the classroom. Remember, students follow the tone set

by the teacher in the classroom. Students observe not only the verbal directives and interactions but the non-verbal cues from the teacher.

Finally, during formal or informal oral presentations or conversations, teachers may correct the content of what ESL students say, if necessary rather than how they say in terms of pronunciation or grammar. Constant interruptions or corrections will deter students from speaking up and sharing their ideas (Gupta 1999).

Often English teachers complain that children in a foreign language sometimes have to be able to do things they cannot do in their native language. Often it is the mastery of different reading technologies, the formation of skills in different forms of writing, for example, highlighting keywords / key information, taking notes, recording a lecture by ear and so on. Many problems arise in the development of oral speech. Speech skills and similar rhetoric. Some skills, such as arguing, separating the primary from the secondary, establishing cause-and-effect relationships, using different methods of presenting ideas, communicating with the listener, and so on. The problem of the teacher and therefore of his students is that, in the teacher's opinion, if something is easy and understandable to him and is explained to him once in a lesson, he will automatically do it for his students. Remains clear and understandable. . Sometimes it happens that the teacher gives the students tasks that he can barely do on his own.

The essence of the methodological component of the curriculum is that the teacher not only explains the new material in the learning process and organizes its correct processing, but also offers his students certain algorithms for completing the tasks, giving them teaches basic methods of independent work. Because foreign language teaching involves the formation of the necessary linguistic, verbal, and socio-cultural competencies, teaching different aspects of language and different types of speech activities involves teaching different ways of working with the concept of a methodological component of teaching content. Dictionary, grammar, phonetics, various types of dictionaries and reference books, as well as methods of working with text, including your own. Students should also be taught to conduct socio-

cultural observations in the process of learning languages and cultures together. To do this, you can use a variety of memo-instructions.

While language teaching has acquired a practical character, it has previously been relatively abstract and theoretical. Even Aristotle gave rise to the famous triad of teaching ethics, which best meets modern requirements: logos – the quality of presentation, pathos – communication with the audience, ethos – attitude to others. This rule applies to both the speaker and the actor, as well as to the foreign language teacher, whose role includes both the first two incarnations. During the teaching process, the teacher's responsibilities changed significantly. A teacher-tutor, a teacher-dictator cannot provide students with the freedom to choose and the "freedom to learn" needed to understand a sensitive issue such as language. Consequently, such a negative pedagogical image is gradually becoming the property of history. He was replaced by a teacher-observer, a teacher-mediator, a teacher-sucker, and a leader. The impact on the audience, in turn, will be closer. Does not decrease, on the contrary, most modern – a teacher who is the organizer of group interaction in Russian and foreign courses (currently learning a foreign language. The ideal team for is a group of 10-15 people, because this is the number of people who can communicate with each other with maximum impact, interest and benefit).

The development and radical changes in language learning methods are undoubtedly related to innovations in the field of individual and group psychology. Now there are significant changes in the minds of people and the development of new thinking: there is a need for self-awareness and self-awareness, announced by A. Maslow. The psychological factor of learning a foreign language is gaining ground. The authenticity of communication, balanced demands and claims, mutual benefit, respect for the freedom of other people – these are the unwritten rules of building a constructive relationship in a "teacher-student" system. Fifth, but the most important element of this system is choice. He emerged as a student who could attend a course that best suited his needs. In the classroom, the student is no longer limited in his choice of means of speech and in his own verbal behavior. The teacher

is also not limited in choice: teaching methods and techniques – from games and trainings to simultaneous translation; in the organization of lessons; In the selection of textbooks and manuals – from a wide range of local publications to products from Oxford, Cambridge, London, New York and Sydney.

increasingly diverse environment of today's classrooms provides a rich opportunity for teachers and students to engage in effective learning. With a growing number of English Language Learners worldwide, there is a critical need for general education and resource teachers to know how to effectively build and implement literacy programs that are inclusive of students' language and culture. Understanding that culture goes beyond the knowledge of ethnic attire, music, food, and language; it includes the total being, comprised of the totality of the student's background, heritage, ancestry, educational, political, and life. The importance of teaching ESL students is critical in the current climate with increasing accountability by way of student performance on standardized tests. ESL students are expected to be on grade level proficiency within three years and teachers are held accountable for their learning (Curtin, 2005).

There are a variety of terms that have been used for non-native English speakers, ranging from LEP (Limited English Proficient), ESL students (English as a Second Language), Bilingual students and English Language Learners (ELL). For practical purposes, we use the term ESL students for a student whose mother tongue is not English. As educators, we understand that ESL students have to double their efforts in school, to not only learn new information but also learn the academic language of the school. Freeman and Freeman (2011, p.19) state, "ESLs face double the work of native English speakers. They must learn English, and they must learn academic content through English. In addition, they often live in neighborhoods where the schools are underfunded and are staffed by inexperienced teachers." On the same note, teachers of ESL students face double work of teaching core competencies enlisted in the curriculum to meet the benchmarks and teach English to non-native speakers. It is a double-whammy. While we realize that no two students are alike and that no two students have the same needs, there are

commonalities among learners that help us approach our teaching in a more informed way. The paper proposes foundational principles and practices for teachers who work with ESL students in their classrooms.

Children will learn English speaking skills as well as speaking skills in other languages, in primary and secondary school. Learning how to develop English speaking skills is so important for ESL students and EAL students too. It's one of the most important parts of language learning as speaking is how we tend to communicate in everyday life.

Speaking is an interactive process where information is shared, and if necessary, acted upon by the listener. So, it's important to develop both speaking and listening skills in order to communicate effectively.

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